

Low-Melting Composite Filler Metals

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SUMMARY

Composite filler materials with low melting ranges and adjusted technologies are especially developed for joining temperature-sensitive AMCs. Due to the addition of ceramic reinforcement components, an improvement of mechanical properties is achieved. In the investigations, the influence of thermal treatment during the joining process on the temperature-sensitive base material is shown.

Keywords: composites, filler material, ultrasonic soldering, creep resistance, particle reinforcement

INTRODUCTION

There has been an increased demand for light-weight composite materials in the last years. In particular aluminium matrix composites (AMC) are applied in many different industrial fields such as aerospace industry, automobile production or power electronic devices. AMCs produced by ECAE (equal channel angular extrusion) are a special group of composites. These materials are characterized by a very high strength due to an ultra-fine-grained structure. Because of their marked temperature sensitivity, an adapted joining technique is required (Refs. 1 -5).

In this regard, soldering offers some advantages in comparison to other joining processes like welding or bonding. Due to their low melting range below 300 °C, Sn-based solders are suitable filler metals for this purpose. Ag and Cu are common alloying elements. The low strength and creep resistance of the joints are disadvantageous features. An improvement of these properties can be achieved by the addition of ceramic reinforcement particles such as Al₂O₃ or SiC. The composite filler metals are produced by high-energy milling (HEM). Already in previous investigations, a significant increase in joining strength and creep resistance could be achieved for a temperature range between 20 °C and 150 °C (Refs. 3, 6 - 10)

Zn fillers are an alternative to the use of particle-reinforced Sn solders. They are characterized by a higher joining strength and creep resistance. The higher working temperature of about 400 °C has an adverse effect. To avoid grain growth, the joining process has to be very short. For this purpose, a combined induction-ultrasound joining process has been developed (Ref. 11).

In the present work, the influence of thermal treatment during the joining process on the properties of the base material is investigated. Therefore, the hardness of the base material is used as an indicator for thermally induced degradation.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

For the investigations, the aluminium matrix composites EN AW-2017(SFB) + 5 / 15 vol.-% (Al_2O_3)_p are used. The alloy EN AW-2017(SFB) has a composition of 3.9 wt.-% Cu, 0.7 wt.-% Mg, 0.6 wt.-% Mn, balanced Al. Three different types of materials are compared: samples without Al_2O_3 particles, with 5 vol.-% and 15 vol.-% of Al_2O_3 particles. All materials were solution heat-treated at 505 °C for 60 min, water-quenched and then immediately processed by equal-channel angular pressing (ECAP). ECAP was performed for one pass at room temperature with 50 mm·min⁻¹ in a die set with an intersection angle of 120° between the channels (outer arc 0°). It resulted in an equivalent plastic strain of ~0.67. The friction conditions inside the die set were optimized by two movable walls in the inlet channel and a moving bottom slider in the outlet channel (Ref. 1). In order to ensure homogeneous deformation and to prevent the specimen from cracking, an active backpressure of 270 MPa was applied via the moving bottom slider. It is important to consider that an additional passive backpressure is induced by the frictional force at the slider bed. After processing, the billets were aged naturally for about one month (T4 condition). Details on the workability and different thermo-mechanical treatments of the investigated matrix alloy are presented in Ref. 2.

Figure 1: Combined induction-ultrasound joining process and specimen dimensions

For joining, a combined induction-ultrasound process was used (Figure 1). Short heating times and local heat treatment are its advantages. Fluxless wetting occurred because of an additional ultrasonic treatment for 30 s. For heating, a Frisch HFL-02/5 with a power of 5 kW and a duty cycle of 14.5 s was used. Before joining, the filler was applied by friction soldering. In view of the reachable joining strength, this method has turned out most useful for further investigations (Ref. 11). The dimensions of the specimens are shown in Figure 1.

The used fillers consisted of SnAg3.5 + 10 vol.-% (Al_2O_3)_p reinforced with ceramic particles and ZnAl5 (Refs. 4 - 10). The joining temperature of SnAg3.5 + 10 vol.-% (Al_2O_3)_p was approx. 280 °C and that of ZnAl5 was approx. 420 °C. The temperature-time regime for the process steps “filler application” and “joining” is given in Figure 2. It can be seen that the application duration of ZnAl5 (110 s) is nearly half

that of SnAg3.5 + 10 vol.-% (Al₂O₃)_P (190 s). This longer period in the case of the particle-reinforced Sn solder is necessary because of worse wetting and flow behaviour.

The joining process shows a high heating rate for both fillers, which is typical for induction heating processes. After achieving the process temperature, ultrasonic treatment was applied for 30 s. Following, the specimens are cooled down to approx. 180 °C for SnAg3.5 + 10 vol.-% (Al₂O₃)_P and 200 °C for ZnAl5, and then they were quenched.

Figure 2: Temperature-time regime of the process steps “filler application” and “joining” for the fillers SnAg3.5 + 10 vol.-% (Al₂O₃)_P and ZnAl5

Brinell hardness, indicating the deterioration of the properties of the base material due to the thermal treatment was measured (according to EN ISO 6506-1) after the process steps “filler application” and “joining”. For this purpose, the specimens were cut perpendicular to the gap in the centre plane. Before performing the hardness measurement, the surface was prepared metallographically.

Induction heating is a locally acting process which is based on the skin effect. Due to this fact, the properties of the base material can be changed according to the distance from the gap. That is why the Brinell hardness was measured at 7 points along the longitudinal axis (length: 20 mm) at the edge and in the middle of the specimens, as shown in Figure 3. Based on these results, the decrease in strength could be estimated.

The microstructure of the soldered joints was investigated by SEM, too.

Figure 3: Scheme of Brinell hardness measurement

RESULTS

The results of the investigations can be divided in four parts: microstructure, comparison of Brinell hardness along the longitudinal axis, decrease in Brinell hardness after filler application and decrease in Brinell hardness after joining.

Microstructure

The microstructure of soldered joints using the investigated fillers is given in Figures 4 and 5. In previous investigations, a good bonding between matrix and reinforcement component has been ascertained [Ref. 5 - 8]. This is an important factor for the intended increase in joint strength by the addition of ceramic reinforcing particles. In Figure 4, a transfer of the Al_2O_3 particles from the base material into the soldered seam can be observed due to the influence of ultrasonic treatment. These particles are larger (10 - 30 μm) than the ceramic particles in the reinforced filler $\text{SnAg3.5} + 10 \text{ vol.-% } (\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3)_\text{P}$ (approx. 2 μm) and non-uniformly distributed.

Figure 4: Soldered joint, filler $\text{SnAg3.5} + 10 \text{ vol.-% } (\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3)_\text{P}$, base material EN AW-2017(SFB)

Figure 5: Soldered joint, filler ZnAl5, base material EN AW-2017(SFB) + 15 vol.-% $(\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3)_\text{P}$

Comparison of Brinell hardness along the longitudinal axis

Figure 6 illustrates the results of the hardness measurements along the longitudinal axis. For both fillers, no difference between the edge and the middle of the specimens can be detected. The values are also similar along the longitudinal axis (point 1 – 7). The reason for these homogeneous properties is the high thermal conductivity and the small dimensions of the specimens ($\varnothing 17 \times 40$ mm).

Figure 6: Brinell hardness, measured along the longitudinal axis (edge and middle) of the specimens after joining for the fillers SnAg3.5 + 10 vol.-% (Al₂O₃)_P and ZnAl5

For both fillers, a decrease in hardness due to the joining process is observed. That is approx. 30 % for the mating with SnAg3.5 + 10 vol.-% (Al₂O₃)_P and approx. 40 % for ZnAl5 in comparison to the initial state after ECAP. It can be seen that a homogeneous decrease in hardness occurs resulting from the thermal treatment during joining. The value of the decrease depends on the used filler, the respective temperature-time regime and the state of the base material.

Decrease in Brinell hardness after filler application

The results of the hardness measurements of the initial state (after ECAP) and after the filler application are shown in Figure 7. After the ECAP process, the unreinforced material has a lower hardness than the AMCs with 5 and 15 vol.-% of Al₂O₃ particles. Also, an increase in hardness with increasing particle content is obtained. This can be explained by the prevention of deformation by ceramic particles.

Figure 7: Comparison of Brinell hardness for initial state (after ECAP) and after **filler application** by SnAg3.5 + 10 vol.-% (Al₂O₃)_p and ZnAl5

After the filler application, an obvious decrease in the hardness of the base material occurs for both fillers. Thereby the application of the particle-reinforced filler SnAg3.5 + 10 vol.-% (Al₂O₃)_p leads to a markedly lower hardness decrease (12 %) in comparison to ZnAl5 (40 %) due to its the lower process temperature. The hardness relationship between the three different base materials is maintained after the filler application. That means the AMCs obtain higher values as the unreinforced material.

Decrease in Brinell hardness after joining

After joining, a higher hardness decrease compared to the filler application is expected due to the longer thermal treatment. Figure 8 shows that this fact is true for the use of the particle-reinforced filler SnAg3.5 + 10 vol.-% (Al₂O₃)_p with an assigned average decrease of 25 %. Contrary to expectations, the hardness of the base material soldered with ZnAl5 filler remains unchanged. The degradation of the properties of the base material occurs already at such a high level during filler application that the thermal treatment of the joining process does not show any effects.

In comparison to the measured hardness decreases, the use of the ZnAl5 filler results in a considerably higher joining strength of up to 240 MPa compared to the particle-reinforced filler (max. 35 MPa). These results are detailed in Refs. 6 and 11. The tensile tests have also shown that the cracking always occurs in the joining zone. A failure of the base material could not be detected, that means the strength of the base material is higher than the joining strength.

Figure 8: Comparison of Brinell hardness for initial state (after ECAP) and after **joining** with SnAg3.5 + 10 vol.-% (Al₂O₃)_p and ZnAl5

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the influence of thermal treatment during soldering of the aluminium matrix composites EN AW-2017(SFB) + 5 / 15 vol.-% (Al₂O₃)_p and the alloy EN AW-2017(SFB) on material properties has been investigated. In order to do that, Brinell hardness measurement has been used. For joining, a combined induction-ultrasound process has been used and the fillers have been SnAg3.5 + 10 vol.-% (Al₂O₃)_p reinforced with ceramic particles and ZnAl5.

1. The thermal treatment of the joining process leads to a decrease in the hardness of the base material, thus a degradation of the mechanical properties occurs.
2. The use of ZnAl5 entails a faster and higher hardness decrease compared to SnAg3.5 + 10 vol.-% (Al₂O₃)_p due to the lower process temperature.
3. Even though the hardness decrease has occurred, the tensile tests have shown that the strength of the base material is higher than the joining strength.
4. To preserve material properties, new joining technologies with a high energy density and local heat treatment are necessary.

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